

Interlinked process, product & data quality framework for zero defect manufacturing

D9.2

Data Management Plan

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ABSTRACT / EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	
Abstract	<p>The goal of this Deliverable is to describe the processes used to manage the data produced in the context of InterQ and shape a Data Management Plan (DMP) in compliance with the applicable legal framework, and in particular the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). As per European Commission (EC) directions, the processes formalized and applied a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data management framework, with the goal of making data openly accessible and interoperable, while enriching them with metadata to ensure their reusability.</p> <p>More specifically, the purpose of the InterQ DMP is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - comply with the Horizon 2020 Open Data Access Guidelines. - promote the Horizon 2020 Open Research Data Pilot initiative. - embed the InterQ project in the EU policy on data management which is increasingly geared towards providing open access to data funded by the EU. - ensure that all possible data is accessible to other researchers, helping to streamline the research process from start to finish and maximize the benefit to society. <p>This Deliverable presents the DMP that identifies the types of data generated or collected by the project and describes the entire data management lifecycle. In addition, it identifies which of them would be suitable for open access following project closure and the standards that will be used for data representation. Special emphasis has been given to address the practices enforced by InterQ for the protection of personal data in compliance with GDPR covering, including any ethics considerations as well as the consent forms and internal processes that InterQ plans to apply.</p> <p>This document also outlines the key Data Management responsibilities of the Work Package Leaders, Project Management representatives from each consortium member, the Project Coordinator and the Data Owners.</p> <p>The InterQ DMP is a public, live document, built to evolve throughout the InterQ project lifespan, capable to capture and reflect evolution in the form of dataset updates and/or changes in Consortium policies. The final version, planned for the end of the project, will outline the details of all InterQ datasets, validate compliance with the different data protection regulations and ensure full access and reusability of the project generated data.</p>
Keywords	InterQ, Data Management Plan, Data sharing, Data privacy, GDPR, Data sets, FAIR Management, Open Research Data Pilot

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
CC	Creative Commons
CNC	Computer Numerical Control
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
FAIR	Findable Accessible Interoperable Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Policy
IP	Intellectual Property
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

This report has been prepared in the context of WP9 and Task 9.3 of InterQ. It covers the InterQ's Data Management procedures as well as internal General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR¹) compliancy policies.

This report is submitted to the European Commission (EC) as the InterQ's Initial Data Management Plan (D9.2) and will be considered as a living document that will be complemented with the actual "Data Management Plan" (D9.3) to be delivered in month 36.

1.1 Context, Scope and Objectives

This Deliverable provides the initial DMP that InterQ will follow throughout the project execution and duration. The report also covers the process to be followed respecting the EC template on FAIR data management, along with any ethics and legal issues related to GDPR policies developed in InterQ for the protection of personal data.

The report in its initial form describes the datasets that will be created, processed and shared within InterQ and how these data relate to the project objectives and the WP structure. The procedures agreed towards Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable (FAIR) data management (as per the EC directions) have also been incorporated, towards the objective of making data findable including provisioning of meta data, making data openly accessible and interoperable, and addressing data re-use considerations and processes.

1.2 Relationship to Other Project Outcomes

This deliverable is the first release of the InterQ's DMP and describes in detail the data produced, distributed within the project. It is mostly taking the internal perspective of GDPR compliance and FAIRness, along with making some of the generated data openly available, in a project context and during the project lifecycle. The final version of the InterQ DMP will be released in month 36 of the project in the context of the deliverable D9.3.

It is worth mentioning the relation with D6.5, which is more practical and context specific, with the goal to ensure that the right guidelines are in place for the security and governance of data used in the project and for easier external adoption of the project solutions. The key differentiator is the "external" perspective of the guidelines in D6.5 and their applicability to other manufacturing ecosystems, not only in the context of InterQ.

The complementarity of these two deliverables guarantees an integrated framework for the data quality, data security and data privacy as well as for the transparency of the InterQ results.

1.3 Structure of the Document

The structure and a short description of each section follows:

Section 1 is the introductory section of the deliverable.

Section 2 is the analysis of the Data Management Plan.

Section 3 is the description of the data sets per WP.

Section 4 outlines the FAIR principles and contributions to Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP).

Section 5 reports any Ethics considerations related to InterQ's data.

¹ GDPR, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504&qid=1532348683434>

Section 6 summarizes the InterQ's GDPR policy.

Section 7 Conclusions.

Annex I: Data Management Report

Annex II: Advisory Board - Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA)

Annex III: GDPR Policy

2 InterQ Data Management Plan

This section includes the InterQ DMP which describes the data management life cycle for the data to be collected, processed and/or generated by the project. It includes data flows in the context of specific use cases, structured reports for the evaluation of the process and information on:

- the handling of research data during & after the end of the project
- what data will be collected, processed and/or generated
- which methodology & standards will be applied
- whether data will be shared/made open access and
- how data will be curated & preserved (including after the end of the project).

2.1 Data Lifecycle

In this section, the entire data lifecycle taking place in the project is analysed. The different stages at which data will be created, processed and/or utilized during the execution of the project and afterwards are considered. What follows, supported by Figure 1 below, is an analysis of the data lifecycle as well as the means to control, manage and report the related data. In each of the sections that follow, specific metrics for the data management and control have been included and are later summarized into the data management report template (Annex I: Data Management Report) that will be used at various project stages to ensure compliancy of the stakeholders with the data management plan. The following diagram demonstrates an indicative typical InterQ data lifecycle, without excluding the potential of alternative data flows throughout this lifecycle.

Complementary analysis regarding the data lifecycle in InterQ is documented in D6.5 Security, Data Management and Governance, but from the perspective of data quality and towards the acceptance of the InterQ outputs by the prospect user community. Moreover, guidelines for the security and data governance are shaped to ensure proper communication between the WPs.

Figure 1: InterQ Data Lifecycle

2.1.1 Data Creation/Collection

As implied by the title, this stage includes the data creation and/or collection as it relates to the various data generated within the InterQ activities and demonstrations as well as the project reports and other documents/spreadsheets. This includes the creation of the data by each of the respective owner and the collection in a structured approach, appropriate format, and layout to enable their processing by the rest of the project components/modules. Specific evaluation criteria at this stage relate to the following:

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	CSV, XLS, XML, etc.
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available, non-corruption, whole percentage collected (e.g. verifiable by hash functions)	100% received 100% accessible
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	100% usable by intended beneficiary/ies
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Including 100% of information for the intended purpose
Relation	Data following a precise relation to their purpose	100% purpose precision

2.1.2 Data Processing and Analysis

This stage is related to the actual data processing by the various data processors that are the project partners who will have access to the data for management following the project needs and outcomes. The processing of the data in a concise way by the suitable partners needs to be guaranteed in order to fulfil the InterQ needs. This stage includes all steps towards data verification, organization, transformation, integration and extraction for the intended use. Data analysis [1] is the next stage and is tightly connected with the data processing previously described. It includes all the actions/methodology executed on the actual data that describe existing facts, identify outlines, develop data clarifications etc. Specific evaluation criteria at this stage are:

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data follow precise data logic
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing	100% organized data
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant	100% validated and relevant data
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach	100% aggregate-able data

Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose	Data properly calibrated

2.1.3 Data Publication and Utilization

The stage of publication of data refers to the capability to share data openly (external to InterQ) whereas the stage of utilization includes the steps towards data sharing (internal to InterQ). A data agreement should be included as part of the data when sharing them openly, see D6.5 section 5. Data Sharing Policy for more details. This implies that the data should be medium and agent independent making sure that the transfer can be implemented in an automated approach. The purpose at this stage is to ensure that the data are shared based on the appropriate controlling mechanisms to ensure protection of proprietary data as well as the data integrity itself [1]. This stage is closely linked to the following one (Data Storage and Archiving) as far as metadata is related to ensure data search-ability (as another feature of the FAIR data treatment, see FAIR Data Management). Specific evaluation criteria at this stage relate to the following:

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach	100% means independent transferability
Security (a)	Data stored in a secure server	By minimum access control provided over a TLS protocol

2.1.4 Data Storage Archiving and Secondary Use of Data

The storage and archiving stages are also very critical as they relate to the data access, sharing, storage, archiving (including search capabilities), disposal and the secondary use of data. Once again, a data agreement would define the context under which the re-usage of data will be appropriately carried out by the interested actors, as described in D6.5 section 5. Important metrics here include the updated status of the data so that no later versions exist (unless is clearly indicated). Actions to ensure accidental data losses, corruption and unauthorized access should be also included. Data storage and archiving is also strongly linked to data re-usability that is also within the scope of the FAIR data management. Specific evaluation criteria at this stage relate to the following:

Performance Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists	100% updated
Meta Data	Existence of meta data in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per data set
Security (b)	Access control provided	Access control setup
Security (c)	Server is considered as safe enough (TLS connection protocol)	At least TLS connection configuration

Bandwidth	Control of server bandwidth	Effective storage server bandwidth > 2 MBPS
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date noted

2.2 Data Flows in InterQ

Data in InterQ will be streamed from Industrial equipment as well as from external physical or virtual sensors to the Cloud for preprocessing, storage, analysis and further exploitation. More details on these data flows can be found in D6.5. The links of Figure 2 show the data flows in the Energy use case of InterQ but can be also considered as a more generic data flow diagram of the project.

Figure 2: Data Flows example from the Energy Use Case

2.3 Data Management Report

The table in Annex I: Data Management Report will consolidate the formal confirmation by each InterQ WP leader on the compliance of key indicators for each WP, as agreed in this deliverable for proper management of the data elements. It will also be included in the final version of the DMP in D9.3 Data Management Plan update.

In addition, the WP7 task leaders will explicitly declare and confirm that data created, processed, stored and shared during the Laboratory and Industrial demonstrations follow the principles of the Data Management plan.

2.4 Metadata

The owners of each data component will be responsible for using the proper naming and tagging conventions following the InterQ quality manual (see D9.1 Project Quality Handbook and project website), so the respective metadata information can be easily kept, extracted and referenced for all purposes of data handling and utilization within InterQ.

InterQ considers metadata provisioning and searching capabilities of primal importance and will be used as the channels to enable data interoperability. Interoperability aspects of the InterQ data have been included in section 3 Data sets in InterQ as well as the summarizing table in section 3.1 InterQ Data Description per WP as far as usage and utilization are concerned. Well agreed and proper data/file naming conventions combined with file tagging and advanced search capability will enable and maximize data interoperability inside InterQ.

Data interoperability is considered only for internal purposes of InterQ and includes data re-use, interchanges and general utilization. For data interoperability outside the consortium, InterQ will follow IPR rules to ensure no InterQ foreground is released. For more details on data sharing outside the consortium as far as IPs are related, see section 6 General Data Protection Policy (GDPR) of this report.

As far as filename conventions are concerned to maximize data interoperability, the consortium seeks to comply with commonly used filenames such as .XML, .XLS(X) etc. Apart from the aforementioned, commonly used standards (relating to commonly used filenames). If need to, InterQ will investigate the possibility to follow other (internationally recognized) standards for both actual data and software produced. Metadata standards (such as ISO 19115 (GIS data), 14721 (Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS), 16363 (audit and trustworthiness of digital repositories)). Compliance to these will support digital data management in a longer-term mentality. Other (software related) ISO standards will be also investigated (such as ISO 25010: ref systems and software engineering) and SQuaRE (systems and software quality requirements and evaluation) [2].

3 Data sets in InterQ and the InterQ Demonstrations

This section defines the data collection concepts and data purposes as they relate to the project's work-breakdown structure. Means of data collection, types of data that will be collected and formatting of the actual data are some of the items that are described based on WP leaders' input.

What follows is a definition of the data that will be created/distributed for each of the InterQ WPs. Data types may include narrative texts, numbers, images, audio files, video files, internal/external reports.

3.1 InterQ Data Description per WP

This section outlines the data produced or processed at each WP and elaborates a number of factors for each of the involved data objects. Each WP's introductory subsection addresses the intended purpose of use of the provided data from the *Data Owner's* perspective and relates them to the InterQ's objectives while the table structure below elaborates for each data element, the following vital information:

- Short description of data content and type
- Data origin/source (where the data come from)
- Data format
- Confidentiality level (Public, Project Consortium, Data Processor(s), Research Purpose)
- Processing/Usage preconditions (restrictions)

3.1.1 WP1 – Requirements Definition

The first WP of InterQ is dedicated to the requirements definition and will not produce any data that should be analyzed or shared. The main output of the WP1 is the four deliverables that will be shared within the consortium. Additionally, the general use-case description will be made public through the project website to describe the activities of the project to the public.

Table 1: InterQ WP Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/Preconditions
Use-case description		html	Public	Anonymised
Deliverables	Partners	.docx	Project Consortium	N/A
Online meetings minutes	Partners	.docx	Project Consortium	N/A

3.1.2 WP2 – InterQ-Process

InterQ-Process aims at controlling the quality of the manufacturing process and equipment. New physical and virtual sensors will be implemented in the machine tool to evaluate the critical process parameters and contribute to the Product-Data-Process quality hallmark. The data generated by this WP will come from physical sensors, machine tool, models and virtual sensors.

InterQ-Process will collect data from the machine tool of the different end-users. Those data are highly sensitive for the end-users so their access will be limited to a selected group of partners that will contribute to the use-case. Apart from the end-user machines, InterQ-

Process will also generate data during the experimentation phase of the project on the laboratory demonstrators and on dummy parts. Those data will be less sensitive and might be shared publicly. However, at this point of the project, the data that will be made public has not yet been identified.

Table 2: InterQ WP2 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/Preconditions
CNC machine	CNC/PLC	.csv	Confidential	N/A
New sensors	Acquisition system	.mat	InterQ-Process	N/A
Operator feedback	Operators	To be defined	InterQ-Process	Only for involved partners
Virtual sensors	Artificial intelligence algorithms	.csv database	+ InterQ-Process	Only for involved partners

3.1.3 WP3 – InterQ-Product

To create digital twins for process monitoring and rapid error localization, the reliability, latency and quality of the data gathered is a matter of critical importance. Based on it and the objective's definition for the monitoring process of each machine used during the manufacturing of the use cases (e.g., machine-data acquisition, and geometry and surface inspections) new physical and virtual sensors will be implemented, along with data from visual inspection devices and the CNC itself in the machines used to manufacture the use cases. Based on cutting-edge communication technologies, new structures are being developed to transfer, process and analyze the data gathered from the different sensors deployed on real-time.

UPV/EHU is in charge of two of the use cases of the project, the manufacturing process of a low-pressure turbine case dummy and the broaching process of fir trees.

Table 3: InterQ WP3 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/Preconditions
Low-pressure turbine case dummy.	CNC Siemens 840D operate V4.9	.csv .xml	Research purpose	Data will be available at CFAA private cloud.
Broaching process	Accelerometer PCB ICP® Model 604B31	.csv .xml	Research purpose	Data will be available at CFAA private cloud.
Broaching process	CNC Fagor 8070 OL	.csv .xml	Research purpose	Data will be available at CFAA private cloud.
Measuring process	Mitutoyo Crysta Apex C162012		Research purpose	Data will be available at CFAA private cloud.

3.1.4 WP4 – InterQ-Data

InterQ-Data aims at generating data quality hallmarks from sensor data observed during the manufacturing process across the different use cases. These data quality hallmarks are based on:

- a) in-motion data validation at the analog source of sensors attached to machine tools such as CNC machines

- b) historical data validation by temporal clustering of data from CNC machines
- c) repaired erroneous sensor data or virtual sensor data based on data from other operational sensors.

The data to achieve this is available both as static datasets and real-time sources of data from services. We also use public domain data to illustrate concepts that are then applied to data from internal partners such as IDEKO and use case owners from aerospace: ITP Aero/Aeromec, automotive: Renault, and energy: Gamesa. We describe the available data sources to the best of our knowledge at the time of writing this document (April 2021), in the following table.

Table 4: InterQ WP4 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/Preconditions
CNC Milling Tool Wear	Kaggle https://www.kaggle.com/shasun/tool-wear-detection-in-cnc-mill	Multiple CSV files for manufacturing a simple part. It is 48 variables from the CNC machine over several minutes.	Creative Commons (CC) 1.0: Public Domain	https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/
Dual accelerometer data from machine tools	IDEKO's internal machines	A continuous stream of data is available at 1Hz. It is composed of top 5 frequencies and amplitudes along with severity.	Internal to WP4-Data members	Only for use internally and aggregate information for publication
Predict's existing data from the automotive domain	Predict	Available on their platform CASEM for development of historical data validation algorithms	SINTEF, PREDICT	At the moment only used by SINTEF and PREDICT
Aerospace: Mid Turbine Frame casing (MTFC) –external turning (8h)	ITP Aero/Aeromec CNC Siemens 840D operator V4.8	CNC and PLC internal signals through OPC to ITP aero's internal data lake. It also include 60 external signals such as pressure, flow current consumption and sensors on turning heads.	Relevant InterQ partners	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC – internal turning (8h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A

Aerospace: M TFC external finish turning and scallop milling/drilling (4h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: M TFC external axis milling (7h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: M TFC internal finish turning and scallop milling/drilling (10h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: M TFC internal 5-axis milling. Milling of internal features (anti rotation slots +Bosses) (14h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: M TFC Deburring and edge finishing (8h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC FPI and Visual test (2h)	FPI and visual inspection according to supplier specs	File with categorial values about product pass/fail as per spec.	-do-	Data should be used for data reliability, increasing ramp up and reducing scrap rate and predicting product quality
Aerospace: MTFC CMM Measuring (9h)	Robotic laser profiling for edge break and radii measuring	File with profile information about MTFC	-do-	-do-
Aerospace: MTFC dummy part made by Basque Country university	University of Basque Country, CNC Siemens 840D operator V4.9	Data available from CNC is stored in edge computing box by SAAVY systems. Direct connection between CNC and CFAA cloud. Additional accelerometer data from external sensors.	Maybe used for research	Data to be used for reducing surface defects, tool breakages, unexpected machine parameters, reduce number of dimensions out of tolerance
Aerospace: MTFC dummy part made by Basque Country university	-do-	Image data for surface defects, frequency of occurrence, impact etc.	Maybe used for research	Data can be used to finish relationship between production parameters and defects

product quality data				
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) - Rough Turning (8h)	ITP Aero/Aeromec CNC Siemens 840D/Fanuc32i	CNC and PLC internal signals through edge compute box. Also direct connection to ITP Aero internal data lake from Siemens CNCs	Relevant InterQ partners	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) -Finish Turning (8h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) Drilling/Milling (4h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) Broaching (5h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) Grinding (4h)	-do-	No monitoring data. Only wheel balancing and crash sensor detectors.	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) -Edge finishing (4h)	-do-	CNC and PLC internal signals through edge compute box. Also direct connection to ITP Aero internal data lake from Siemens CNCs	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) dummy ring (CNC Fagor 8070 OL, Multicomponent Dynamometer – Kystler Type 92255B Mitutoyo Crysta-Apex S9106 Optris PI 160	Virtual Machine on Smart Network for Industry (SN4I) Data acquisition and normalization on VM and available there.	Maybe used for research and demonstration for InterQ-Data	Data can be used for InterQ KPIs: reduce unexpected non controlled machine parameters, reduce surface defects, reduce dimensions out of tolerance by 70%, employ existing sensors for process monitoring

Energy: Wing turbine planet carrier (WTPC)	CNC Sinumerik 840D Solution Lin	N/A	Relevant InterQ partners	N/A
Energy: WTPC – product quality	Coordinate measuring machine (CMM)	N/A	-do-	N/A
Energy: WTPC demonstrator case	CNC Siemens 840 Dsl v4.8		Maybe used for research and the final demonstrator for InterQ-Data	
Energy: WTPC demonstrator case	CMM at the Metrology lab of Tekniker	Monitoring software is installed in Beckhokk industrial PC in the Zayer machine. Smart Factory Cell is visualized and analyzed	-do-	N/A
Automotive: Renault's Cleon Engine cylinder head	CNC machines from COMAU	Most likely a continuous stream of data from the CNC machine. Also perhaps available on Predict's CA SEM system	Relevant InterQ partners	N/A

3.1.5 WP5 – InterQ-ZeroDefect

InterQ-ZeroDefect aims at the utilization of the data concerning the manufacturing process and products, generated in WP2 and WP3, and pre-processed in WP4 with the ultimate goal of Zero-Defect-Manufacturing. This goal will be approached by developing a software framework for Virtual Quality Management which consists of multiple interconnected components. The InterQ Quality Hallmark Dashboard module will monitor and track quality-related KPIs of the entire production line and act as the Human-Machine-Interface between the Machine Learning components used for quality prediction, optimization, and machine condition monitoring. Internally, the framework utilizes a digital twin of the production line to optimize process parameters of single machines as well as holistically. Further, the digital twin is used to speed up process capability assessment in case of production line reconfiguration. The database used to achieve this goal is the “output” of WP4 InterQ-Data:

- a) Sensors attached to machine tools and inbuild data acquisition devices in CNC machines
- b) Repaired erroneous sensor data or virtual sensor data based on data from other operational sensors
- c) Structured and unstructured data describing product and production line configurations
- d) Process capability information
- e) Reading of measurement machines regarding specified dimensions of parts

The data to achieve this is available both as static datasets and real-time sources of data from services. WP5 also uses public domain data to illustrate concepts that are then applied to data from internal partners such as IDEKO and use case owners from aerospace: ITP Aero/Aeromec, automotive: Renault, and energy: Gamesa. The available data sources to the best of our knowledge at the time of writing this document (April 2021), can be found in the following table. Especially the data description regarding the automotive use case at Renault is still underdefined and will be expanded as more information becomes available.

Table 5: InterQ WP5 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/Preconditions
PTW CNC Machine Process Data	PTW Machines (TBD)	TBD	Project Consortium	N/A
PTW Measurement Machine Data	PTW Machines (TBD)	TBD	Project Consortium	N/A
CNC Milling Tool Wear	Kaggle https://www.kaggle.com/shsun/tool-wear-detection-in-cnc-mill	Multiple CSV files for manufacturing a simple part. It is 48 variables from the CNC machine over several minutes.	CC1.0: Public Domain	https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/
Tennessee Eastman Process Simulation Dataset	https://dataverse.harvard.edu/dataset.xhtml?persistentId=doi:10.7910/DVN/6C3JR1	RData Files containing data from 52 process variables (measurements and parameter) of a TEP simulation	Available online, free access	NA
Dual accelerometer data from machine tools	IDEKO's internal machines	A continuous stream of data is available at 1Hz. It is composed of top 5 frequencies and amplitudes along with severity.	Internal to WP4-Data members	Only for use internally and aggregate information for publication
Predict's existing data from the automotive domain	Predict	Available on their platform CASEM for development of historical data validation algorithms	SINTEF, PREDICT	At the moment only used by SINTEF and PREDICT
Aerospace: Mid Turbine Frame	ITP Aero/Aeromec C	CNC and PLC internal	Relevant InterQ partners	N/A

casing (MTFC) – external turning (8h)	NC Siemens 840D operate V4.8	signals through OPC to ITP a ero’s internal data lake. It also includes 60 external signals such as pressure, flow current consumption and sensors on turning heads.		
Aerospace: MTFC – internal turning (8h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC external finish turning and scallop milling/drilling (4h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC external axis milling (7h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC internal finish turning and scallop milling/drilling (10h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC internal 5-axis milling. Milling of internal features (anti rotation slots +Bosses) (14h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC Deburring and edge finishing (8h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: MTFC FPI and Visual test (2h)	FPI and visual inspection according to supplier specs	File with categorial values about product pass/fail as per spec.	-do-	Data should be used for data reliability, increasing ramp up and reducing scrap rate and predicting product quality
Aerospace: MTFC CMM Measuring (9h)	Robotic laser profiling for edge break and radii measuring	File with profile information about MTFC	-do-	-do-
Aerospace: MTFC dummy part made by Basque Country university	University of Basque Country, CNC Siemens 840D operate V4.9	Data available from CNC is stored in edge computing box by SAAVY systems. Direct connection between CNC and CFAA	Maybe used for research	Data to be used for reducing surface defects, tool breakages, unexpected machine parameters, reduce number of dimensions out of tolerance

		cloud. Additional accelerometer data from external sensors.		
Aerospace: MTFC dummy part made by Basque Country university – product quality data	-do-	Image data for surface defects, frequency of occurrence, impact etc.	Maybe used for research	Data can be used to finish relationship between production parame ters and defects
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) -Rough Turning (8h)	ITP Aero/Aeromec C NC Siemens 840D/Fanuc32i	CNC and PLC internal signals through edge compute box. Also dire ct connection to ITP Aero internal data lake from Siemens CNCs	Relevant InterQ pa rtners	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) -Finish Turning (8h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) Drilling/Milling (4h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) Broaching (5h)	-do-	-do-	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) Grinding (4h)	-do-	No monitoring data. Only wheel balancing and crash sensor detectors.	-do-	N/A
Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) -Edge finishing (4h)	-do-	CNC and PLC internal signals through edge compute box. Also dire ct connection to ITP Aero internal data lake from Siemens CNCs	-do-	N/A

Aerospace: Low Pressure Turbine Disc (LPTD) dummy ring (CNC Fagor 8070OL, Multicomponent Dynamometer – Kystler Type 92255B Mitutoyo Crysta-Apex S9106 Optris PI 160	Virtual Machine on Smart Network for Industry (SN4I) - Data acquisition and normalization on VM and available there.	Maybe used for research and the final demonstrator for InterQ-Data	Data can be used for InterQ KPIs: reduce unexpected non controlled machine parameters, reduce surface defects, reduce dimensions out of tolerance by 70%, employ existing sensors for process monitoring
Aerospace: Structured and unstructured data describing product and production line configurations	Production line	-do-	-do-	N/A
Energy: Wing turbine planet carrier (WTPC)	CNC Sinumerik 840D Solution Lin	N/A	Relevant InterQ partners	N/A
Energy: WTPC – product quality	Coordinate measuring machine (CMM)	N/A	-do-	N/A
Energy: WTPC demonstrator case	CNC Siemens 840 Dsl v4.8		Maybe used for research and the final demonstrator for InterQ-Data	
Energy: WTPC demonstrator case	CMM at the Metrology lab of Tekniker	Monitoring software is installed in Beckhokk industrial PC in the Zayer machine. Smart Factory Cell is visualized and analyzed	-do-	N/A
Energy: Structured and unstructured data describing product and production line configurations	Production line	-do-	-do-	N/A
Automotive: Renault's Cleon Engine cylinder head	CNC machines from COMAU	Most likely a continuous stream of data from the CNC machine. Also perhaps available on Predict's C ASEM system	Relevant InterQ partners	N/A
Automotive:	Production line	-do-	-do-	N/A

Structured and unstructured data describing product and production line configurations				
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3.1.6 WP6 – InterQ-TrustedFramework

The role of the InterQ-TrustedFramework is, as far as data management is concerned, to provide a trustworthy common registry for key elements of QA-related information: identities, data sets used for the calculation of quality indicators and PPD quality hallmarks. Backward traceability means that hallmarks are immutable, non-repudiable and can be traced back to data sets and the identities of the data sources.

Table 6: InterQ WP6 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Identity descriptors of the active actors of supply chain / quality management processes (e.g., companies, departments, smart machines)	Process stakeholders (manual acquisition)	Blockchain record (extended form of standard DID Document)	Project consortium	Identified elements may be faked for PoC purposes; when not, they must never contain personal data
Identity descriptors of the passive elements of supply chain / quality management processes (e.g., product types, product items, sensors, workflows)	Process stakeholders (manual acquisition)	Blockchain record (extended form of DID Document)	Among involved parties	Identified elements may be faked for PoC purposes; when not, they must be unambiguously linked to the real-world or virtual entities they represent
Trusted data sets	Output of quality measurement factory systems	Blockchain record (proprietary data model) + cloud-stored BLOB object (original data set)	Among involved parties	n/a
Quality hallmark indicators	Output of quality assessment factory systems	Blockchain record (proprietary data model)	Among involved parties	Indicators must be unambiguously linked to the trusted data (see previous row) they are calculated from

3.1.7 WP7 – Laboratory and industrial demonstrations

WP7 is about showcasing the benefits of the InterQ framework, module by module, by creating PoC demonstrations in realistic industrial environments. While the demonstration is taking place, WP7 will measure (in a 3D machine) one part from each machine involved in the project per day and will record data from the machine center that can be monitored in real-time. InterQ Trusted Framework will enable traceability of each part and monitoring of the machine conditions during the production of the parts.

Table 7: InterQ WP7 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/Preconditions
Laboratory part measures	Zeiss Coordinate measuring Machines / QDAS	.dfq .txt .pdf	Among involved partners	
Machine process parameters	Comau MC	.csv .txt	Project Consortium	
Traceability of the parts	QR codes readers / Web intelligence /SAP	Database	Project Consortium	
Sensor records		TBD	Among involved partners	Requires the installation of sensors in the previous phases of the project
Other Process parameters	SAM	.pdf	Project Consortium	

3.1.8 WP8 – Exploitation, Communication and dissemination

The objective of WP8 is to enhance the impact of the technical project developments. Two main activities are included: first, the dissemination of project results, where data/information related with the project will be shared with a broad range of public as industrial stakeholders, scientific community or even general public; and second, to determine the best strategy to exploit project results.

WP8 will primarily develop and implement a Communication and Dissemination plan, formalize the strategies for commercializing the results of the project, with special attention to IP protection and provide recommendations for policies. In most cases, the information that will be shared will be public and will be required to be agreed by the consortium. In cases that information (e.g. personal data, pictures) of persons involved directly (partners) or indirectly (advisory board, European commission personnel) is included in the communication material, explicit agreement will be required.

The current information that WP8 is gathering in relation to the Advisory Board members is the following:

- name,
- email address,
- organisation and the role the AB members,
- whether the member has sent a letter of interest for the proposal,
- whether the member has filled the InterQ NDA document, presented in Annex II
- the member's expertise in relation to InterQ, and
- the responsible InterQ partner/person

The aforementioned information is considered as 'personal' information. The data are kept only for the purpose of the project (and for its duration) and only with the consent of the Advisory Board members, as this will be acquired via a clear consent statement (also included in Annex II: Advisory Board – Non-Disclosure Agreement).

Table 8: InterQ WP8 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/ Preconditions
Posters, flyers	Custom made for InterQ	Pdf	Public	Design agreed by Project consortium
Website, Social media	LinkedIn, Twitter, Web		Public	Design agreed by Project consortium Contents agreed with involved partners.
Photo, images, video	Retrieved during physical or virtual project events, Custom made for InterQ	Common formats for pictures (jpg, png, ...) and videos (asf, avi, mpeg)	Public	Explicit consent received from appearing participants, Lawful use-rights granted from media owners
Questionnaires, reports...	Custom made for InterQ	docx	Public	Contributors details either anonymised or simply consolidated
Presentations (workshops, conferences...)	Custom made for InterQ	Pdf, pptx	Public	InterQ template needs to be used. Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory
Scientific publications	InterQ outputs	pdf	Public	Open Access Contents agreed with involved partners. Acknowledgements to EU funding is compulsory

3.1.9 WP9 – Project Management

WP9 is the project management WP and it is responsible for the technical and administrative coordination of the project including also the quality and ethical activities. These tasks will create and process various types of documents and files in order to ensure the efficient and effective management of InterQ. These types of data will consist of documents, spreadsheets or presentation files, for managing and handling content related to meetings such as agendas, meeting minutes, presentations etc. in MS office (or similar) type of documents (.doc/.docx, .xls/.xlsx, .pdf, .ppt/.pptx etc). All partners are expected to have access to them while they will always be considered as internal documents to the InterQ consortium (not to be distributed outside InterQ). This also includes all documents and spreadsheet files for the collection and progress/periodic reporting (internally and/or to the EC) of InterQ. These will be circulated internally to the consortium or submitted as final versions to the EC and will be mainly MS office documents (.doc/.docx, .xls/.xlsx, .pdf etc). Patenting files will also be considered as internal documents so they should fall into the above category and type of data.

All related files in WP9 are restricted to the InterQ consortium and will be stored in the InterQ web-space (Microsoft Teams server) where all partners have fully controlled and safe access through secure authorization mechanisms. Links for exchanging these files internally will be circulated via email or the Microsoft Teams server itself.

Other files that will be created in the framework of WP9 consist of quality management and templates for all the above (and possibly more) purposes. These files will most of the time be .doc, .docx, .pdf, .xls, .xlsx, .ppt, .pptx files created by the Quality Manager and used and shared by the InterQ partners.

Finally, the collection and processing of personal or sensitive data is not anticipated in the context of WP9. If in any case during the project, this condition is no longer valid, an explicit confirmation that the beneficiary has lawful basis for processing the respective data must be provided in written to the Project Coordinator, along with the confirmation that the appropriate technical and organisational measures are in place to safeguard the rights of the data subjects. This confirmation will be included in the final version of the Data Management Plan.

Table 9: InterQ WP9 Data Mapping

Data Description	Data Origin/Source	Data Format	Confidentiality	Restrictions/Preconditions
Meeting presentations	Partners and Coordinator	.ppt, .pptx	Consortium Internal, unless agreed to be public	Consortium Internal, unless agreed to be public
Management and financial reports (internal and EC)	Partners and Coordinator, EC	.doc, .docx, .pdf .xls, .xlsx	Consortium Internal	
Deliverables and internal reports	Partners and Coordinator, EC	.doc, .docx, .pdf	Depending on Deliverables' GA defined type, Reports are internal	
File for patents	Partners and Coordinator	.doc, .docx, .pdf	Consortium internal until patent filling	
Other templates (minutes, agendas etc)	Quality management templates	.doc, .docx, .pdf .xls, .xlsx, .ppt, .pptx	Consortium Internal	

3.2 WP leaders' Responsibilities and Allocation of Resources

InterQ does not allocate any budget resources specifically for the data management. WPs include all relevant budget resources, such as the technical effort, management of the WP, as well as management of the related data. WP9 and specifically T9.3 carries the overall responsibility for the data management and lifecycle monitoring for all datasets to be created, collected, shared or processed by the project.

Towards the goal of ensuring compliance with the previously described data management processes of each WP as they relate to the DMP, the following overall InterQ measures will apply:

- WP leaders will be responsible for adhering to the specifications above in their WPs.
- The Project Manager of each organization will be responsible for the DMP actions and will be accessible by the rest of the team in case of issues related to the DMP.
- Data owners have the ultimate responsibility of complying with the specifics of the InterQ DMP, as well as the related GDPR policies.
- The Project Manager and the primary contact from each and every partner should ensure that personnel working on the project have read the DMP and apply/exercise all the principles as described in the InterQ DMP (this document).

4 FAIR Data Management and the ORDP

FAIR data management relates to the EC guidelines [3] on the Data being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reused. Data will be created, acquired and collected in all InterQ's WPs and will include the following: Reports (internal or external to InterQ) in text, MS Word and other text files, MS XLS or other spreadsheets, MS PowerPoint files (presentations), audio files (.wav, .mp3 etc.), multimedia files (video recordings and other), specification documents (text), software application source code files, software application executable files, other observation material, survey questionnaires and data, factsheets, project images, etc. (see Table 1, Table 2, Table 3, Table 4, Table 5, Table 6, Table 7, Table 8 and Table 9).

As the following sections reveal, we relate FAIR data management to naming conventions, contribution to open data research, data identification and searching, as well as meta-data provisions and data reusability.

4.1 FAIR Data Management

InterQ will implement several actions described below to act in accordance with the FAIR principles.

Making data findable, including provisions for metadata:

- The datasets will have very rich metadata to facilitate the findability. Open data format (csv, xml) will be used.
- All the datasets will have Digital Object Identifiers provided by the public repository (ZENODO).
- The reference used for the dataset will follow the format: "InterQ_Process_Datatype_XX" (XX: identifier to be added for similar datasets).
- The standards for metadata will be defined for each dataset as described in Section 2.4.

Making data openly accessible:

- The datasets that will be openly available will be described according to Table 10.
- The datasets for evaluation will be accessible via InterQ's Microsoft Teams Server.
- The datasets will be made available using a public repository (e.g., ZENODO) after the project.
- Table 10 and Table 1 will be used to explain the methods or software used to access the data. Basically, no software is needed to access the data.
- The data and their associated metadata will be hosted in a public repository or in an institutional repository.

Making data interoperable:

- The metadata vocabularies, standards and methodologies will depend on the public repository and use the recommendations of section 2.4.
- The InterQ will define a common data format or reuse an existing one. This work is being developed in close collaboration with Task 6.4 Security, Data Management and Governance with the goal to follow a single format across the project.

Increase data re-use (through clarifying licenses):

- All data producers will license their data to allow the widest reuse possible. Examples of licenses are available at <https://opendefinition.org/licenses/>.

- By default, the data will be made available for reuse. If any constraints exist, an embargo period will be mentioned in Table 10 to keep the data for only a period of time.
- The data producers will make their data available for third parties within public repositories. The data will be reused for the scientific publication's validation purpose.

4.1.1 Naming Conventions for InterQ documents and data/document versioning

Within the framework of the InterQ quality plan and control, a series of documents/reports and templates will and have been created to ensure a consistent approach for all InterQ data and their versions. Details about these reports can be found in InterQ D9.1 "Project Quality Handbook and project website". For purposes of completeness, we have added below some common material to indicate how the data versioning is aligned with the FAIR approach. Partners use the Microsoft Teams server of the project for the development of the documents, which enable collaborative writing and track changes functionalities. For any case that versioning management is applied, the guidelines below should be followed:

- The file name should start with "InterQ_**"
- The filename should be descriptive of the contents and the author, e.g. "InterQ_D9p1_q_Report_IDK_v2.docx"
- When a document is likely to be produced in a similar format by various partners, the partner's short name should be included in the file name.
- When commenting on a document provided by another partner, the filename should be changed to include the initials of the person or short name of the partner making the changes e.g. "InterQ_**_IDK_v2_AER.docx" if changes to the version 2 have been made by Aeromec.
- When suggesting changes to a document, the use of the track changes feature in Word is recommended to assist the document author/owner.
- Only the originating author or owner of a document should increment the version number, i.e. when the author has received and implemented all changes to the second version of the document, it becomes "InterQ_**_IDK_v3.docx".

4.2 Contribution to the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP)

Open Access (see Figure 3) is about offering on-line access to scientific information, cost-free to the end-user and in a multiple-use fashion. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' refers to peer-reviewed scientific research articles published in scholarly journals and research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data) [4].

Figure 3: Open Access in H2020 projects

The ORD pilot aims to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data generated by InterQ and takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialization and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions. The project, along with the publication of scientific publications, will deposit at the same time the publication of research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited publications ('underlying data'). Publication of data within InterQ will be accomplished on a voluntary basis by the stakeholders, and in full alignment with the Intellectual Property (IP) and the patenting activities of InterQ. It is recognized that some research data cannot be made open and the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" will be applied.

Considering the above, InterQ aims at contributing data to the ORDP. Data sets that are candidates for sharing will certainly have been inspected to make sure that:

- They are not confidential, that they do not include commercially sensitive or personal info according to GDPR (Annex III: InterQ GDPR Policy).
- That permission from the relevant stakeholders and/or data objects has actually been obtained.
- That sharing the data does not damage exploitation or IP protection prospects.

The project will create a public repository in ZENODO to deposit Open Data following the FAIR data principles to ensure findable, accessible, interoperable data and to increase their re-use. The next version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) will explicitly specify what data will be open, how it will be exploited or made accessible for verification and re-use, and how it will be curated and preserved.

Accordingly, datasets will be reviewed by the *Data Owners* and must be approved before becoming candidates for contribution to the open research. These parties and the respective technical consortium partner(s) will then agree on the licensing (e.g. creative commons or public domain). Following in principle approval, InterQ will then make the dataset available through the InterQ user community and upload content to the existing relevant and suitable open access repositories. Where data must be embargoed towards IP protection or exploitation, a timeline for its release will be provided.

The approval of the availability of data in an open approach will need to be sent to the project coordinator from the actual *Data Owners* via email. For this, a consent that the data can be distributed outside the consortium must be included in the approval email to the project coordinator. The following information should be included:

Table 10: Open Data Ownerships

Data Owner	Description of data	Data filenames and version	Consent to publish data outside the InterQ consortium
<i>Who is the data owner</i>	<i>What the data include</i>	<i>Filenames and depository position</i>	<i>[YES/NO]</i>

5 Ethics considerations

It is assumed that all data to be collected from stakeholders in the project will be done in accordance with applicable ethical standards and requirements in the respective countries of the data collection, as well will be processed and handled in a secure way and in line with applicable rules and regulations on privacy and data protection.

Specific articles of the Grant Agreement (GA) mandate that all ethical principles comply to the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity, avoiding fabrication, falsification, plagiarism or other research misconduct. In chapter 4, section 4 of the GA, Article 34 ETHICS AND RESEARCH INTEGRITY and Article 39 PROCESSING OF PERSONAL DATA, dictate the roles and responsibilities of each consortium partner, since they are beneficiaries of the InterQ. Towards InterQ's objectives, the beneficiaries have full responsibility for implementing the action and complying with the provisions of the GA. Regarding compliance with Ethics principles, each beneficiary must submit to the coordinator in good time notifications for activities raising ethical issues. Additionally, obligations of all partners related to Data management are described in the other sections of this deliverable.

6 General Data Protection Policy (GDPR)

As of May 2018, the GDPR has been applicable in all Member States in the European Union, as well as in the countries in the European Economic Area (EEA).

Data confidentiality is an overriding concern throughout the InterQ project and beyond, as the InterQ framework will continue to be used afterwards, thus InterQ aims at being fully GDPR compliant. All data to be collected from stakeholders in the project will be done in accordance with applicable ethical standards and requirements in the respective countries of the data collection, as well will be processed and handled in a secure way and in line with applicable rules and regulations on privacy and data protection.

Table 11 below presents the data and personal information that is planned to be collected and stored throughout the project duration and beyond as well as their access, storage, purpose and retention details. The InterQ's GDPR policy is described in detail in Annex III: InterQ GDPR Policy.

Table 11: Data and Personal Information from day-to-day activities

Personal Data Description ²	Access ³	Storage ⁴	Purpose ⁵	Duration ⁶
Official Contact List of InterQ contacts	Internal to InterQ (project partners only)	InterQ's Microsoft Teams Server (team: InterQ - Consortium, <i>folder: InterQ Contacts</i>)	Management, organizations contact points	31/10/2023
Meetings' related material (agendas, presentations, signature lists, minutes)	Internal to InterQ (project partners only)	InterQ's Microsoft Teams Server (team: InterQ - Consortium, <i>folder: Meetings</i>)	Knowledge sharing, dissemination and management reasons	31/10/2023
Workshops/Conferences and Training sessions	Internal and external to InterQ	InterQ's Microsoft Teams Server (team: InterQ - Consortium, <i>folder: Meetings, InterQ Website</i>)	Large event dissemination	31/10/2023
Reporting (C forms)	Internal to InterQ (project partners only)	InterQ's Microsoft Teams Server (team: InterQ - Consortium, <i>folder: Project's Official Documents</i>)	InterQ reporting and consolidation of financial reports	5 years after the project's end

² Overall data description.

³ Determines who has access to the particular data (internal, external to consortium).

⁴ Storage places of actual data.

⁵ Intended purpose of data and reasons for keeping.

⁶ Duration of stored data (until when they will be kept).

Deliverables, official documents and other InterQ reports	Depending on deliverable type could be public or consortium restricted	InterQ's Microsoft Teams Server (team: InterQ - Consortium, <i>folder: Project's Official Documents</i>)	InterQ documents and deliverables	31/10/2023
Publications	Internal and external to InterQ	InterQ's Microsoft Teams Server (team: InterQ - Consortium, <i>folder: Project's Official Documents</i>)	Dissemination and publication of research results	Internal: 31/10/2023 External: Depending on publisher

7 Conclusions

This document is the first release of the InterQ's DMP and describes in detail the data and the mechanisms to manage them in the context of the InterQ project. It includes a detailed introduction of the data that will be produced, processed or used within the InterQ scope with details on the type and nature of the data involved in each of the InterQ WPs, as well as their relationship with the project goals. A structured approach has likewise been developed and recorded to make sure that InterQ's data management follows the FAIR data concepts as specified by the EC.

A full section of this report has been devoted to address the security of personal data in compliance with GDPR (regulation) that has been developed to harmonize data privacy legislations throughout Europe, and also protect as well as enable all EU citizens' data privacy, by improving the methods that companies throughout the area approach data privacy. This section also covers all practices that InterQ will follow to abide by the above, along with consent forms and internal processes that InterQ prepared to implement and use.

References

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Annex I: Data Management Report

Indicator	Means of verification	Target Values	Compliance
			WPX
Data Creation			
Format	Compliance with existing standards of data exchange	XLS, XML etc.	√ or ×
Availability and Readability	Whole package of data available, non-corruption, whole percentage collected	100% received 100% accessible	√ or ×
Fit for Use	Data follow data compliancy for proper processing and review	100% usable by intended beneficiary/ies	√ or ×
Consistency and Completeness	Data are consistent and complete for the intended purpose	Including 100% of information for the intended purpose	√ or ×
Relation	Data follow a precise relation to their purpose	100% purpose precision	√ or ×
Data Processing and Analysis			
Data logic	Data can be and are processed following a concise logic and approach	New and processed data follow precise data logic	√ or ×
Organization and Utility	Suitable content organization of data under processing	100% organized data	√ or ×
Validation	Ensuring that the data under processing are correct and relevant	100% validated and relevant data	√ or ×
Aggregation	Whenever multiple data need to be aggregated ensure that this is done in a concise approach	100% aggregate-able data	√ or ×
Transformation	Transformation of data to the proper format(s) for processing	Capability of data for transformation (if needed)	√ or ×
Calibration	Calibration of data for their intended purpose	Data properly calibrated	√ or ×
Data Publication and Utilization			
Means-independent	Transferring of the data in a means-independent approach	100% means independent transferability	√ or ×
Security (a)	Data stored in a secure enough server	At least access control provided over a TLS protocol	√ or ×
Data Storage, Archiving and Re-Use			
Up to date	Ensuring that the stored data are up to date for the specific purpose and no later version exists	100% updated	√ or ×
Meta Data	Existence of meta data in stored files	Relevant metadata have been included into the archive per data set	√ or ×
Security (b)	Access control provided	Access control setup	√ or ×
Security (c)	Server is considered as safe enough (TLS connection protocol)	At least TLS connection configuration	√ or ×

Bandwidth	Control of server bandwidth	Effective storage server bandwidth > 2 MBPS	√ or ×
Expiration	Properly setting expiration dates for all data after which the data will be deleted	Expiration date noted	√ or ×

Annex II: Advisory Board – Non-Disclosure Agreement

Non-Disclosure Agreement for Advisory Board Members

This Non-Disclosure Agreement (“NDA”), is made as of 30/04/2021 hereinafter referred to as “Effective date”, and is entered into by and between the following parties (each a “Party and collectively the “Parties”):

(1) IDEKO S COOP (IDEKO), established in CALLE ARRIAGA 2, ELGOIBAR 20870, Spain, VAT number: ESF20147773, represented for the purposes of signing the Agreement by Izaskun ABAUNZ.

(2) <Advisory Board member details>.

-AND-

The other Parties above are hereinafter each referred to as a “Advisory Board Party” and collectively as the “Advisory Board Parties”.

WHEREAS the Project Coordinator of project “InterQ” funded by the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 958357 has entered into a consortium agreement (the “Consortium Agreement”), with effective date November 2021, regarding InterQ.

The Advisory Board Parties are members of an advisory committee (the “Advisory Board”), connected to InterQ, but are not necessarily partners in InterQ (in which case not parties to the Consortium Agreement). The Advisory Board Parties will not commit any financial resources to this project but will contribute expertise as identified in the stages of the project, subject to availability and a voluntary approach. Therefore, the Advisory Board Parties will not receive any direct costs, however travel and accommodation costs related to InterQ events and/or meetings, will be reimbursed by providing the respective receipts to the coordinator (IDEKO).

WHEREAS, the Project Coordinator, for the mutual benefit, anticipate the need to disclose to and receive from each other information regarding InterQ, which the disclosing Party considers to be proprietary and which relates to the Advisory Board Parties’ participation in the Advisory Board (hereinafter referred to as the “Project”).

The Parties are aware that the Consortium Parties’ undertakings towards each other regarding confidentiality and non-disclosure are governed by the Consortium Agreement and consequently not by this NDA.

NOW, THEREFORE, in consideration of the covenants and agreements herein contained, the sufficiency and adequacy of which are acknowledged, the Parties agree as follows:

1. “Information” as used in this Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) is any information disclosed by a Consortium Party to an Advisory Board Party related to the Project or by an Advisory Board Party to a Consortium Party related to the Project. A Consortium Party or an Advisory Board Party who discloses Information pursuant to the first sentence of this Article 1 is hereinafter referred to as a “Disclosing Party”. An Advisory Board Party or a Consortium Party who receives Information pursuant to the first sentence of this Article 1 is hereinafter referred to as a “Receiving Party”.

2. All information in a tangible form (including information transmitted electronically) which the Disclosing Party desires the Receiving Party to treat as “Confidential Information”, shall be marked by the Disclosing Party with the legend “CONFIDENTIAL” or “PROPRIETARY” in order to identify its confidential nature. If Confidential Information is disclosed orally, visually or in any other non-tangible manner of disclosure, such information shall also be entitled to protection as Confidential Information, if the information disclosed is identified as Confidential Information at the time of disclosure and is subsequently reduced to appropriate written form and furnished to the Receiving Party within one (1) month of the time of original disclosure.

3. Each Party hereto agrees to receive Information from the other Party for the sole purpose of evaluating the progress and research results of InterQ.

4. For the term of the confidentiality obligation provided for in this NDA, the Receiving Party agrees to hold the Confidential Information received from the Disclosing Party in confidence and not to disclose such Confidential Information to any other Party or party and to use such Confidential Information only for specified purposes in this NDA. The Receiving Party agrees that it will use the same degree of precaution and safeguards as it uses to protect its own information of like importance, but in no case with any less than reasonable care. For the avoidance of doubt, the Receiving Party also agrees that it will not use Confidential Information to develop or produce any product or to develop or perform any service without an agreement in writing with the Disclosing Party authorizing such development, production or performance.
5. The obligation of confidentiality shall not apply to:
- (i) Information, which is now or later becomes publicly available through no act or failure to act on the part of the Receiving Party in violation of this NDA; or
 - (ii) Information, which the Receiving Party can prove is rightfully acquired by the Receiving Party from a third party which is not under any obligation of confidentiality with respect to the Information; or
 - (iii) Information, which the Receiving Party can prove is developed by or for the Receiving Party independently of information which the Receiving Party is required to keep confidential under this NDA; or
 - (iv) Information, which is required to be disclosed by national law or any court having jurisdiction over the Receiving Party; or
 - (v) Information, which the Receiving Party can show it possessed before the Disclosing Party disclosed it to the Receiving Party
6. The Receiving Party may disclose Confidential Information to its employees who need to know and use Confidential Information in furtherance of the purposes of this NDA and who are under an obligation to keep the Confidential Information confidential to the same extent as the Receiving Party.
7. The Receiving Party will return Confidential Information to the Disclosing Party upon written request by the Disclosing Party. However, the Receiving Party will be allowed to retain one (1) archival copy of any document if required by national law.
8. The Agreement shall cover Confidential Information disclosed by the Disclosing Party to the Receiving Party for the purpose of this NDA. Termination of obligations of confidentiality and non-use shall not be construed, however, as a grant of any license under patent rights or copyrights of the Disclosing Party, any other Party or party.
9. Nothing contained in this NDA shall obligate any Party to enter into any agreement with any other Party for the purpose of any development project or for any other purpose. Also, this NDA does not include, expressly or by implication, any representations or warranties as to the accuracy, efficacy, completeness, capabilities, safety or any other qualities whatsoever of any Information or materials provided under this NDA, nor does this NDA grant the Receiving Party any license on the Information of the Disclosing Party.
10. This NDA shall be construed in accordance with and governed by the laws of Belgium. All disputes arising out of or in connection with this NDA, which cannot be solved amicably, shall be finally settled under the Rules of Arbitration of the International Chamber of Commerce by one or more arbitrators appointed in accordance with said Rules. The place of arbitration shall be Brussels, if not otherwise agreed by the conflicting Parties. The arbitration will be final and binding upon the Parties. Nothing in this NDA shall limit the Parties' right to seek injunctive relief or to enforce an arbitration award in any applicable competent court of law.
11. This NDA can be amended or modified only by an amendment in writing signed by all Parties. Parties foresee to enlarge the number of Advisory Board Parties and agree to amend this NDA for accession upon request.
12. This NDA constitutes the entire agreement and sole understanding of the Parties with respect to the subject matter hereof, save for the Consortium Parties' undertakings towards each other regarding confidentiality and non-disclosure which are, as stated above, governed by the Consortium Agreement and not by this NDA.
13. An entity becomes a Party to this NDA upon signature of this NDA. This NDA shall have effect from the Effective Date and will expire upon complete fulfilment of InterQ. The secrecy obligations last until five (5) years after the expiration of this NDA. Provisions and/or obligations which naturally are intended to continue to exist after the expiration of this NDA, survive such expiration.

14. The Information is provided 'as is' without any kind of warranty, express, implied and/or statutory, including but not limited to the fact that the application and/or use of the Information does not infringe the intellectual property rights and/or other rights of a third party. The Parties are liable towards each other only for damages, which are the direct result of a culpable shortcoming namely a breach of contract, on the part of the breaching Party under this NDA. The Parties are not liable to each other for any kind of other damages, losses, expenses, indirect and/or consequential damages, which the Receiving Party suffers, arising out of and/or in connection with the accuracy, completeness and/or other quality issue with respect to, and/or the application and/or use by the Receiving Party of the Information.

15. The Receiving Party acknowledges and agrees that all property, including intellectual property, in the Information shall remain and be vested in the Disclosing Party.

16. By signing this NDA, the Receiving Party consents to InterQ consortium keeping their personal data (name, email and affiliation) and photos (taken during project events) for the purposes of the InterQ advisory board and only. All parties reserve the right to be removed (opt-out) from the project repository, at any point via direct contact to the project coordinator, in full compliance with the EU GRPR policy.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Parties have accepted the terms and conditions of this NDA and caused it to be duly signed by the undersigned authorized representatives in separate signature pages.

Company name: IDEKO
Signature(s):
Name(s):
Title(s): InterQ Project Manager
Date:

Company name:
Signature(s):
Name(s):
Title(s):
Date:

Annex III: InterQ GDPR Policy

This General Data Protection Policy (the “**Policy**”) is drafted by Inlecom (the “**responsible for the DMP**”) regarding the EU H2020 Project InterQ Contract Number 958357 (the “**Project**”) and is executed by the list of partners included therein (the “**Project Partners**”) to:

- Comply with the policy and legal requirements of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation EU 2016/679, the “**GDPR**”), as in effect since 06 June 2020
- Comply with all other applicable national and EU regulations and guidelines on personal data processing
- Comply with applicable regulations and best practices about research projects within the EU H2020 Research Programme
- Raise awareness and improve knowledge among the Project Coordinator, the Project Partners, as well as their employees and/or agents and/or contractors (collectively, the “**Policy Recipients**”)

Since data protection is a dynamic legal field of constant change, new developments, in the form of new regulations, official reports and/or guidelines, are issued by EU and national legislators as well as competent national authorities, at a constant pace. In this context, this Policy may need to be periodically updated by the Project Coordinator, to remain relevant to legislative change. Accordingly, Policy Recipients will be duly informed, and will be asked to provide their renewed consent upon any such updates.

While every effort has been undertaken by the responsible for the DMP to compile a comprehensive, accurate, relevant and lawful Policy, it is expressly clarified that this Policy does not constitute legal advice neither does it warrant compliance to any applicable laws or regulations. This Policy makes no warranties, express or other, on lawfulness, completeness, fitness for a purpose, or merchantability. Recipients and addressees of this Policy are advised to engage legal counsel prior to applying this Policy for their own aims and purposes.

7.1 Definitions

The GDPR definitions apply, as set in the GDPR Article 4⁷. In addition, and towards the goal of particularizing and complementing the definitions of Article 4, the following terms are introduced. Policy Recipients are advised to consult both texts to formulate the applicable definitions each time.

“**Personal data**” means any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person that is processed by any Project Partner and Policy Recipient during execution of the Project.

“**Controller**” means the owner of the data (usually the creator of the data itself), unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.

“**Processor**” means each Project Partner, unless otherwise expressly clarified in this Policy or elsewhere in Project deliverables and/or reports.

“**Consent**” of the data subject means any freely given, specific, informed, unambiguous and in writing indication of the data subject's wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action, signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her.

“**Supervisory authority**” means the competent Data Protection Authorities within the Project Partners' jurisdictions.

7.2 Policy scope

The Controller determines in advance what is the law applicable to the processing of personal data in a particular case, considering that according to EU law such determination comes from legal principles and cannot be derogated by the parties.

⁷ <http://www.privacy-regulation.eu/en/article-4-definitions-GDPR.htm>

7.2.1 Establishment

Each Project Partner is established on the territory of EU Member States. In the event of any change in establishment, the respective Project Partner shall notify the Project Coordinator duly and in writing.

Unless otherwise expressly specified, each Project Partner is considered the controller in that Member State.

Processor outside the EU

In the event of any subcontracting to an organization not established on EU territory (such as subsidiaries pertaining to the same corporate group) that processes personal data of people staying on EU territory, on behalf of a Project Partner, that organization qualifies as Processor and ensures the fulfilment of the obligations imposed by the GDPR for that specific part of processing.

7.3 Personal data processing

7.3.1 Personal data

Personal data means any information relating to natural persons, that is or can be identified, even indirectly, by reference to any other information including a personal identification number, location data, an online identifier or to one or more factors specific to the physical, physiological, genetic, mental, economic, cultural, or social identity of that natural person.

7.3.1.1 *Special categories of data*

Special categories of personal data include data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation as well as the processing of genetic data and biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying an individual.

In the event of such processing the Controller and/or Processor respectively comply with specific rules related to the processing of such data of special categories, as collecting specific informed consent from data subject and applying stricter safeguards.

When the Controller and/or Processor relies on data subject's consent as a legal ground for processing special categories of data, it will meet all legal consent requirements; otherwise, they are only processed if and to the extent it is based on one of the legal grounds listed in the GDPR for the processing of such data.

7.3.1.2 *Data anonymisation*

Whenever possible, including non-detrimental to Project execution purposes, Controller and Project Partners shall undertake efforts to keep personal data processed by them for Project purposes anonymous or pseudonymous.

According to the GDPR, "*anonymous information*" is information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person, or personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. In this context, the GDPR does not apply to the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes.

Similarly, "*pseudonymisation*" means the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

7.3.1.3 *Newsletters, social media and other dissemination material*

Unless otherwise expressly specified in Project contract, the Controller shall be responsible for the personal data processing carried out for Project dissemination purposes. To this end, the Controller shall:

- Collect and keep all relevant personal data (including lists of contact details), or copies thereof

- Monitor relevant communications
- Address to Project Partners instructions and guidelines on Project dissemination activities (including any EU or other state guidelines, whenever available)
- Inform Project Partners of any policy or legal requirements reviews and changes

7.3.2 Data subjects

7.3.2.1 Minors

Processing of children's personal data requires a special legitimate basis. In the event of such processing the Controller shall be informed in advance and in writing by Project Partners.

7.3.3 Data processing

Data processing means any operation, or set of operations, carried out with or without the help of electronic or automated means, concerning the collection, recording, organization, keeping, interrogation, elaboration, modification, selection, retrieval, comparison, utilization, interconnection, blocking, communication, dissemination, erasure and destruction of data whether the latter are contained or not in data bank.

7.3.4 Principles for legitimate processing

European Union data protection law set forth the following specific principles which must be complied with for the processing to be legitimate.

Pertinence and necessity - The Controller should implement management practices to fulfil the obligation to collect only relevant and necessary data for a specified purpose.

Purpose limitation - Personal data is collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a way incompatible with those purposes. The Controller has a clear overview of all purposes for which personal data is processed. Personal data is not processed for purposes besides the original purposes, unless the (secondary) use is compatible.

Data minimization - Personal data collected by the Controller must be adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary in relation to the purposes for which they are collected and further processed; if the same purposes can be realized in a less data intensive way a preference is given to that method.

Data update - Personal data is accurate, and, where necessary, kept up to date. Every reasonable step is taken to ensure that personal data that are inaccurate, having regard to the purposes for which they are processed, are erased, or rectified without delay.

Data retention - Personal data is kept in a form which permits identification of data subjects for no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. The Controller and/or Processing concerned should have processes and policies in place to:

- determine what the applicable (minimum and maximum) retention periods are for the personal data that is being processed
- ensure that relevant retention periods are monitored

7.4 Data protection legal roles and responsibilities

With regards to the actors involved in personal data processing, the consortium was able to identify the following roles:

7.4.1 Controller

By determining the purposes and means of the processing of personal data, unless otherwise expressly specified in this Policy, the Controller is considered by law as the "Controller" and it is the primary target of the provisions of the law.

"Identification"

The data controller previously identifies itself as such and ensures an effective implementation of data protection measures to comply with the principle that personal data are processed

fairly and lawfully. The legal role of controller implies specific responsibilities because provisions setting conditions for lawful processing are essentially addressed to the controller.

“Accountability”

The GDPR provides full accountability of the company/controller regarding the compliance of its processing of personal data with the law. To ensure the effectiveness of that obligation, it prompts the Controller to follow an overall approach, achieving a genuine system of control and management of its pertinent information. So, accountability and compliance system are elements of the framework for the protection of personal data, in the cause/effect relationship: to be compliant and able to prove it (accountability), the Controller needs to put in place a comprehensive compliance system.

“Data Protection by design”

The Controller considers data protection issues from the outset and from the design of the Project, within the whole lifecycle of processing, to manage the issues in a proactive way, to reduce costs and improve efficiency.

“Data Protection by default”

The Controller standardizes data protection principles in personal data processing, products, and services. The measures adopted ensure that:

- Personal data is processed for purposes not different from the original purposes
- Only data necessary for these purposes are collected
- Data are not disclosed without human intervention

7.4.2 Joint controller

If at any time during Project execution the Controller processes personal data in conjunction with a third party, by jointly determining the purposes and means of the processing, they both act as joint controller. Both joint controllers determine the mutual responsibilities with a specific arrangement.

7.4.3 Processor

Unless otherwise specified expressly in this Policy, all InterQ partners handling personal data are considered as Data Processors, meaning that they process personal data under the control and guidance by the Data Controller.

A processor processes personal data on behalf of the Controller – that is, the Controller delegates all or part of the processing activities to them. In such event the Project contract assumes the role of the relevant required written agreement as per GDPR requirements.

The processor warrants that it shall provide sufficient guarantees to ensure compliance with the GDPR, has implemented appropriate controls to meet data protection requirements defined by the agreement, instructions and/or legal requirements and ensures the protection of the rights of data subjects.

7.4.3.1 Auditing

The Controller ensures the commitment of the Processor(s) to enable and contribute to any review activities, including inspections, carried out by the Controller or other (EU authorities’) auditors and/or reviewers, as appropriate.

7.4.3.2 Security

Each Project Partner undertakes that it adopts appropriate security measures to ensure the security, integrity and confidentiality of personal information and electronic communications at an adequate level with regard to Project purposes, and at any event at no lower level than processing of similar data within its own organisation.

7.4.4 DPO

Whenever required, following applicable GDPR and Member State respective legal requirements, the Controller, and each Processor, may designate a Data Protection Officer ("DPO") for assistance in monitoring internal compliance with GDPR.

“Identification”

Each Processor appoints a DPO in accordance with the criteria and the requirements set forth in the GDPR, as applicable to it. In such event, it shall notify the Controller in writing accordingly.

“Designation compulsory vs voluntary”

Each Processor documents the reasons supporting the designation of the DPO or, rather, the reasons why such designation is deemed not necessary. This documentation forms part of the data protection documentation system of that Processor.

“Professional requirements”

The DPO has sufficient authority, professional qualities and independence to ensure success in his role, according to the GDPR provisions.

“Tasks”

The organization assigns to the DPO at least the tasks listed in the GDPR.

“Notification to Supervisory Authority”

Whenever a DPO is appointed the organization notifies the Supervisory Authority of such designation and publishes DPO's contact details.

7.4.5 People in charge of processing

Individuals who process personal data under the authority of the Controllers or Processor(s) must receive specific formal instructions. Hence, the Controller gives specific instructions, relating also to the implementation of security measures and safeguards, to all its personnel in charge of processing personal data.

7.4.5.1 *Training and awareness*

All Project Partners' employees should be well informed and aware of data protection implications and be able to carry out their obligations in their work. A data protection education and communication program should be in place and supported by a monitoring system that confirms all employees and/or contractors are appropriately trained on their data protection responsibilities.

7.4.5.2 *Policies and procedures*

Data protection policies and procedures exist, are documented in writing, are formally approved by management, implemented, reviewed, updated, and approved when there are changes to applicable laws and regulations.

All Project Partners understand, and the Controller may ask them to overview all their personal data processing, the data protection risks and the applicable rules and procedures. In such event, they shall provide it with all requested information to the best of their ability without undue delay.

7.5 Notice and consent

7.5.1 Notice

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, provides the information required by law to the data subject in a concise, transparent, intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language, in particular for any information addressed specifically to a child.

The data protection notice informs data subjects about the processing of personal data relating to them, even when the personal data is not collected from them as well as of their rights, in order to let them verify in particular the accuracy of the data and the lawfulness of the processing.

7.5.2 Free and informed consent

Personal data is processed if and to the extent that the data subject has given valid consent to the processing for one or more specific purposes, or another legal basis for processing exists.

Systems or applications are able to document the explicit consent of the data subject so that it can be evidenced at any time.

Other legal grounds for a legitimate personal data processing are the following:

1. performance of a contract
2. legal obligation
3. vital interest of data subject
4. public interest
5. legitimate interest of the controller or third party

If "legitimate interest" is used as a basis, the interests that have preceded to the decision, need to be documented as well as any possible mitigating measures which will be taken to be able to proceed with personal data processing based on the defined interests.

7.5.3 Withdrawal of consent

Data subject's consent can be withdrawn at any time; even though it will not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal.

7.6 Rights of data subjects

The individual whom the data refers to (data subject) is entitled with specific rights set forth by the law. The GDPR requires that each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must facilitate the exercise of the data subject's rights, act on the request within a specific time frame and must communicate the information requested in an intelligible and easy to access form.

- Right of access

Any individual must be able to exercise the right of access to data relating to him which are being processed.

- Right to rectification

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request rectification of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases rectification is legitimate. If a data subject's request for rectification is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to erasure

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request erasure of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases erasure is legitimate. If a data subject's request for erasure is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to restriction of processing

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for data subjects to request restriction of processing of their personal data. The procedure specifies in which cases restriction is legitimate. If a data subject's request for restriction of processing is legitimate, this is executed across all relevant data storage facilities, including those managed by third parties.

- Right to data portability

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, determines which processes are subject to the right of data portability as well as when the requirements for such right are met. Data subject can request the organization to receive a machine-readable copy of the personal data the organization holds about them and where possible, enable the transfer of this data to another data controller.

Portability right can be exercised when:

- (a) Processing operations are based on data subject's consent or on contract
- (b) Personal data concerns the data subject and are the same that the latter has provided to the organization
- (c) The right does not adversely affect rights and freedoms of others
- (d) The processing is carried out by automated means

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, implements appropriate measures and procedures to provide data subject, who is entitled to, with a structured, commonly used and machine-readable copy of the personal data it holds about him and where possible, to enable the transfer of this data to another data controller indicated by data subject.

- Right to object

Where personal data are processed for scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, the data subjects have the right to object on grounds relating to their situation (unless the processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of public interest). The right to object is explicitly brought to the attention of the data subject at the latest at the time of the first communication with the data subject, presented clearly and separately from any other information. Measures should be in place to assess such objections and to ensure that such processing ceases when the request is legitimate and needs to be respected.

Data subjects have right to object, on request and free of charge, to the processing of personal data relating to them for purposes of direct marketing.

- Automated decision making

Data subject has the right to object to any automatic decision-making (including profiling).

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, will have determined which processes entail automated decision-making (including profiling) and will have established measures to allow data subjects to object to such automated decision making and profiling. Suitable measures are in place to safeguard the data subject's rights and freedoms and legitimate interest, at least the right to obtain human intervention on the part of the Company/controller, to express his or her point of view and to contest the decision.

- Timely response to exercise of rights

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must confirm to data subjects without delay whether data relating to them are processed and communicate the data to them in an intelligible form. Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should implement internal procedures to be able to provide a timely response to the requests of data subject for the exercise of his rights.

Measures must be implemented in a way that effectively allows an individual to exercise his or her right to personal data, and that enables Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, to respond to such request appropriately within the required timeframes.

7.6.1.1 Notification to recipients

In case of a legitimate exercise of rights to rectification, erasure, or restriction of processing recipients of the personal data should be informed of the rectification, erasure of that data or of the restriction of processing.

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, should have a procedure in place for communicating any rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing to the recipients to whom the personal data has been disclosed and for disclosing these recipients to the data subject, if so requested.

7.7 Data protection documentation system

7.7.1 Register of processing

Each Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, regarding their processing activities must set up a relevant record, maintained in writing (including in electronic form) and made available easily and swiftly to the supervisory authority on request, as per applicable legal requirements within their respective Member States. The record of processing activities shall contain all the information required by GDPR.

Consequently, the Controller shall have an up-to-date overview of all personal data processing activities and shall maintain records within the Project, that meet the legal requirements posed by the GDPR. By so doing, the Controller will be able to demonstrate compliance to any Supervisory Authority or other state or EU authority concerned.

For the avoidance of doubt, each Project Partner carries the same responsibility above within its own respective organisation.

7.7.2 Register of data breaches

A specific register where the breaches must be recorded together with other information specified by the law, must be maintained by the Controller and shown to the Supervisory Authority upon request. This register is an important element of the data protection documentation system.

Project Partners need to notify immediately and in writing the Controller of any personal data breach within their respective organisations that affects execution of the Project in any way, and to cooperate with the Controller while applying relevant GDPR legal requirements.

7.8 Data protection assessment

7.8.1 Assessment

If a Data Protection Impact Assessment (“DPIA”) is carried out under the Project, the Controller shall ensure that personal data receives the appropriate level of protection in accordance with the assessed data protection risk.

The decision whether to carry out a DPIA under the Project, unless undertaken in respective Project contract, will be made by the Controller upon prior written consultation with the Project Partners.

7.8.1.1 Adequacy of protection

The Controller, assisted by Project Partners, should have a process in place to assess for all processing the risks of varying likelihood and severity for the rights and freedoms of natural persons, taking into account the nature, scope, context and purposes of personal data processing.

7.8.1.2 Impact assessment in case of high risk (DPIA)

When the preliminary assessment highlights that processing represents high risks, a formal and documented DPIA is carried out by ascertaining possible impact on data subject. DPIA is conducted in such a way to meet all the requirements set forth by the GDPR (art. 35) to confirm the quality and validity of the findings.

7.8.1.3 Prior consultation to Supervisory Authority

The Controller has a process in place and roles are assigned in order to ensure that when a DPIA determines that the processing represents high risks, the competent Supervisory Authority is consulted prior to the processing.

7.9 Technical and organizational measures

The Controller and each Project Partner, as appropriate, adopts appropriate technical and organisational measures regarding Project execution (the “**Measures**”), and reviews and updates them where necessary, to ensure and to be able to demonstrate that processing is following GDPR.

Each Project Partner shall notify relevant Measures to the Controller in writing. In the event of any queries or further requests by the Controller, each Project Partner undertakes to address them duly and in writing.

If any Project Partner has notified the Measures to its competent Supervisory Authority, it shall inform the Controller thereof, and shall provide respective copies thereof.

7.10 Data breach

According to GDPR, the Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must implement adequate Measures to prevent personal data breaches.

In addition, the Measures should be able to minimize the adverse effects in case a security breach to personal data relating in any manner to the Project occurs anyhow.

Should a data breach occur, GDPR sets forth that the Controller and/or Processor, as appropriate, must notify it to the Supervisory Authority providing specific information, without undue delay and in any case no later than 72 hours from the time of knowledge.

When the breach leads to significant risk of serious adverse effects on the data subject(s) or serious adverse consequences for the protection of personal data, also the latter must be informed without undue delay.

7.11 Data transfers to third countries

No international transfers of personal data are expected to take place under the Project. In the event that any Project Partner wishes to carry out such personal data processing, it shall notify the Controller in writing and in advance. Unless otherwise expressly specified, any international data transfers carried out by any Project Partner for any reason during Project execution take place at its own exclusive liability and responsibility; same Project Partner shall hold all other Project Partners (including the Controller) harmless from any legal or other claims arising for such personal data processing.

7.12 Sanctions and damages

In case of violation of data protection principles and rules, each Project Partner (including the Controller) is responsible for damages and is subject to sanctions. Possible violations may involve civil liability and sanctions in order to ensure that any relevant damage is compensated. The Project Partner (including the Controller) that is liable for said damages and/or sanctions shall hold all other Project Partners harmless from any claims, costs, and expenses arising from relevant GDPR infringement.

7.13 InterQ Web-server Personal Data Protection and Privacy policy

The following Personal Data Protection and Privacy Policy should be uploaded onto the Project Document Server (Microsoft Teams):

1. Introduction. This Personal Data Protection and Privacy Policy (the "Policy") aims at providing details of the processing, and related methods of use, of personal data referred to users/visitors (the "User(s)") of this website that can be reached at the address [<https://teams.microsoft.com/>] (the "Website").

This Policy refers to EU Project [InterQ, 958357], (the "**Project**").

Web users and visitors are recommended to carefully read this Privacy Policy before sending any personal information and/or filling in any electronic form posted on this website.

This information is given in accordance with applicable EU data protection law, in particular the EU General Data Protection Regulation, and EU applicable Privacy law.

2. Controller. The Controller is the actual data owner per data set. Each InterQ partner introducing, transferring, or creating data for the needs of the project is expected to assume full ownership and responsibility of the respective data.

3. Scope. This Policy covers this web site only, and no other personal data processing under the Project or any other websites owned or run in any manner by the Controller or Project Partners.

4. Policy and information notice. This site has been designed with the main function of providing information on the activities of the Project. Therefore, in most cases, the collection of the user's personal data is not required.

In certain instances, such as the "newsletter" section and to allow the transmission of our newsletter, the interested user is required to fill out a data collection form. In these cases, the user is always free to provide his/her own data and consent to relevant processing. We recommend reading this Policy before providing the data.

In addition, should it be necessary in limited cases to collect personal information for other purposes, this will be clearly shown in the information privacy notices required by law, in order to enable transparency and user awareness. Consent forms and other documentation will be used each time, as appropriate.

The above information aims to define limits and methods of personal data processing of each service, according to which the visitor can freely express his consent and eventually allow the collection of data and its subsequent use.

5. Traffic data. The computer systems and software procedures used to operate this website acquire, during their normal operation, some personal data whose transmission is implicit in the use of Internet communication protocols.

This category of data includes IP addresses, browser type, operating system, the domain name, and website addresses from which you are logged in or out, the information on pages visited by users within the site, the time of access, time period of user's staying on a single page, the internal path analysis and other parameters regarding the user's operating system and computer environment.

This technical / IT data is collected and used only in an aggregated and not immediately identifiable manner; they could be used to ascertain responsibility in case of hypothetical crimes against the site or upon public authorities' request.

6. Cookies. No cookies are used by this website.

7. Redirects to other websites. From this website, you can connect through special links to other websites of Project Partners within the Project, or of third parties as applicable each time. Controller hereby assumes no responsibility regarding the possible processing of personal data by third-party sites and in respect of the management of authentication credentials provided by third parties.

8. Purposes of processing and data retention. The processing of personal data is carried out mainly by using electronic procedures and media for the time strictly necessary to achieve the purposes for which the data were collected. The User, however, has the right to obtain the cancellation of his data for legitimate reasons.

9. Optional supply of personal information. The supply of personal data required from the User, unless otherwise noted, is optional, but in case of refusal it could be impossible to fulfill the request, or the related activity mentioned.

10. Place of personal data processing. Data processing related to web services of this website takes place, unless otherwise expressly stated, at Controller's establishment, which provides for the corresponding server management. Personal data are only handled by technical personnel of the Controller, specifically in charge of processing, or others charged with occasional maintenance operations. These persons have received specific instructions on the confidentiality of this data.

11. Scope of data flow and dissemination. The data may be used by Controller and/or Project Partners' employees, as persons in charge of processing, to whom appropriate operating instructions have been given, as well as by third parties who perform operating activities on behalf of them and who act as data processors, to fulfill contractual obligations about the Project. Personal data are not disseminated to unspecified recipients. Detailed information on the names of the data processors can be requested by writing to the project coordinator.

12. Data protection rights. Regarding the processing of personal data, User has the right, at any time, to obtain confirmation of whether the data exists and to have it communicated to him/her in an intelligible format. Users also have the right to know the content and the origin of the data, to check its accuracy or to ask that it be integrated, updated, or adjusted. Finally, Users have the right to ask that the data be deleted or made anonymous or to request the blocking of data processed in violation of the law; moreover, they may oppose the processing of the data for legitimate reasons. Requests should be addressed to the project coordinator.

13. Policy updating. The possible entry into force of new laws, as well as the evolution and updating of User services or developments in the Project could make it necessary to vary the method of processing of personal data. It is therefore possible that our policy may be modified over time and therefore we invite the visitor to periodically visit this page. To this end, the policy document highlights the date of last version.

7.14 InterQ Day-to-Day Data Usage and Related Processes

Even though InterQ does not use any direct personal data (in the form of data coming out or processed during its research activities), it recognises the needs for creating some process related policies so that there is overall agreement of the usage/storage/retention/opt-out etc. of data from every-day (day-to-day) project activities. A list of such matters is included below where the means that the consortium will tackle them reflects the whole consortium agreed approach.

7.14.1 Meetings' related material

This relates to any document created and used for the purposes of project meetings. These may relate to agendas, presentations, minutes, signature lists or any other internal document created for the purposes of InterQ meetings. All these documents will be created and maintained for internal purposes of InterQ and only InterQ partners will have access to them at the InterQ Microsoft Teams server under the meetings folder. They will be kept for 5 years after the project end (for auditing reasons, i.e. 31/10/2028). Any person has the right to opt out of being mentioned in these by direct email to the project coordinator before or after the meeting.

7.14.2 Workshops/Conferences and Training sessions

These data relate to the creation of workshops, agendas, programmes, participants' lists etc. and in general dissemination material related to InterQ-organised workshops. Regarding the external publication, we consider that this material can be fully anonymized so that it excludes personal information from the presenters/participants in the related programmes/agendas that will be shared publicly. For the parts of the related material that will be used for the workshop organisation internally to InterQ, the related files will be stored in the InterQ Microsoft Teams server under the folder meetings. The data will be kept for 5 years after the project end for auditing reasons (i.e., 30/5/2028). Any person has the right to opt out of being mentioned in these by direct email to the project coordinator before or after the event.

7.14.3 Reporting

Reporting refers to internal and external (EC) documents including InterQ progress of activities, technical overviews etc. Related files will be including documents (reports with no personal identifiable information) and financial data (C forms) sometimes including personal data. The purpose of these data is financial so that partners can claim budget requests for their related effort in InterQ. C forms will be maintained by the project coordinator only and stored at an internal and secure server. These (per partner) data are not to be shared with anyone internally or externally to InterQ, will be kept for 5 years after the project end (for audit purposes, i.e., 31/10/2028) and will be deleted after this date. Opting out of these data will be possible but will require an updated Form C to be submitted by the project partner.

7.14.4 Deliverables, internal documents and other InterQ reports

During the InterQ project, a large series of documentation and reporting will be developed relating to the project deliverables and/or internal documents etc. These files will be used for the project contractual obligations and shared to: InterQ partners, EC, everyone (depending on deliverable type). In these documents, the name of authors will be included. Following this, as far as the internal (to InterQ) and EC distributed documents are related, they will be used only for the purposes of reporting and stored in the InterQ's Microsoft Teams server under the Project's Official Documents section. Reports that will be shared publicly (public deliverables) will mention only the partner name and not any other personal information. All reports will be kept for 5 years after the project end for auditing reasons (i.e., 31/10/2028).

7.14.5 Source codes

As far as the inclusion of personal information inside source codes is concerned, InterQ intends to not use any such information into actual source code files produced in the framework of InterQ foreground. In case that any partner wishes to include any personal information, a related consent form will have to be created, used, and signed by the data owner(s).

7.14.6 Usage of cookies (in InterQ sites)

In the cases that in an InterQ application (web) the usage of cookies is needed, a related pop-up window informing the user must be present, prompting the user to accept (or not) the conditions under which her/his personal information are stored. InterQ will maximize efforts to reduce the usage of cookies in its web developments.

7.14.7 Project related research data (data from demonstrations)

Any data circulated internally to InterQ for research purposes (i.e., data from demonstrations for source code analysis, sensor data for analytics etc.) must be fully anonymized by the data owner (in this case the data controller) and not relating in any case to personal information as stated in the sections above.

7.14.8 Any other InterQ related data

In case that personal information needs to be added in any other document in InterQ, the controller (document creator) will have to notify the data owners of their personal details being included into the related document, purpose, retention, storage etc.